

MEASURES TO PROVIDE EMPLOYMENT TO THE YOUTH POPULATION AND PREVENT POVERTY

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KEYWORDS

poverty level, poverty, jobs,
employment, employment with
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ABSTRACT

The development of small business and private entrepreneurship takes a special place in increasing the employment of the able-bodied population and reducing poverty. This article describes the features and importance of innovative business activities in reducing poverty. Proposals for socio-economic development of small business and entrepreneurial entities have been put forward.

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AHOLINING YOSHLAR QATLAMINI ISH BILAN TA'MINLASH VA KAMBAG'ALLIKNI OLDINI OLIISH CHORA-TADBIRLARI

KALIT SO'ZLAR:

kambag'allik darajasi, qashshoqlik, ish o'rinlari, ish bilan bandlik, norasmiy mehnat bilan bandlik

ANNOTATSIYA

Mehnatga layoqatli axolining ish bilan bandligini oshirish va kambag'allikni qisqartirishda kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikning rivojlanishi aloxida o'rin egallaydi. Mazkur maqolada kambag'allikni kamaytirishda inno-vatsion tadbirkorlik faoliyatining xususiyatlari, axamiyati yoritilgan. Kichik biznes va tadbirkorlik sub'ektlarini ijtimoiy-itstisodiy rivojlantirish buyicha takliflar ilgari surilgan.

O'zbekiston Respublikasi iqtisodiy-ijtimoiy rivojlanishida kambag'allik darajasi axolining turmush tarzida ifodalanib, ijtimoiy masala sifatida deyarli barcha iqtisodiy tizimlarda namoyon buladi. Kambag'allik mamlakat iqtisodiy rivojlanishiga salbiy ta'sir kursatgan xolda mehnat bozorida turgun raqobatsizlik xolatini keltirib chiqaradi, iqtisodiy va ijtimoiy tizimlarning uzaro muvozanatini buzadi, shuningdek, axolli xarid qobiliyatining pasayishi evaziga bozor umumiy talabini xam kamaytiradi.

Olimlarning fikricha "Kambag'allik yurtimizda ko'p yillar "yopik, mavzu" bulib, avvallari bu kategoriyaning urniga yumshatish qabilida "kam ta'minlanganlik" tushunchasi bilan almashtirib kelingan edi. Bugun mamlakatimizda olib borilayotgan ochik demokratik siyosat tufayli mazkur muammoning mavjudligi, uning echimi bo'yicha chuqur taxlillarni amalga oshirish, uni pasaytirish va kelajakda bartaraf etish haqida yuksak minbarlarda xam ochik-oydin gapirilmogda. Kambag'allikni kamaytirishning asosiy yunalishlari bulgan norasmiy ish bilan bandlikni qisqartirish va yangi ish urinlarini tashkil etishni ko'paytirish xamda yoshlarni zamonaviy mutaxassisliklar va kasb-xunarlariga tayyorlashni strategik yondashuvlari buyicha amaliy va ilmiy tadqiqotlar ijtimoiy yo'naltirilgan raqamli bozor iqtisodiyoti talablari asosida etarlicha olib borilmaganligi o'rganilayotgan tadqiqot mavzusining dolzarbligini belgilaydi.

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti "Kambag'allikni kamaytirish oylik yoki nafaqa mikdorini ko'paytirish, yoppasiga kredit berish, degani emas. Buning uchun, eng avvalo, aholini kasbga o'qitish, moliyaviy savodxonligini oshirish, odamlarda tadbirkorlik xissini uygotish, infratuzilmani yaxshilash, farzandlarini o'qitish, sifatli davolanish, manzilli nafaqa tulash tizimini joriy qilish kerak deb ta'kidlab ijtimoiy gurux yoki individning xayoy uchun zarur bulgan eng kam extiyojlarini kondira olmasligining iktisodiy sharoitini aks ettiruvchi xususiyat ekanligini yana bir bor kursatib berdi Kambag'allik tushunchasi mehnat qilish, avlodlar uzviyligini davom ettirish hayotiy extiyojlarni qondirish imkoniyatiga ega bo'lmagan shaxs yoki ijtimoiy guruxlarning iqtisodiy holatlarini ifodalovchi kursatkich bulib, ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy xodisa sifatida iqtisodiyotning rivojlanish jarayonida moddiy va nomoddiy imtiyozlardan foydalanish va daromadlarni taksimlashdagi tengsizlikning

oqibati sifatida izohlanadi.

Hozirgi kunda Uzbekistonda 400 mingdan ortiq oila turmush sharoitlari yaxshilanishiga muxtoj. Uzbekiston sharoitida xam rivojlangan mamlakatlardек kambag'allikni qisqartirishga kompleks yondashuv eng maqbul echimdir. Uzbekistonda oxirgi uch yil mobaynida kambag'allikni kamaytirishga qaratilgan chora-tadbirlar natijasida aholi jon boshiga real jami daromad 43,9 foizga, o'rtacha xisoblangan nominal oylik ish xaki 79,7 foizga yoki 2016 yildagi 1293,8 ming so'mdan 2019 yilda 2324,5 ming so'mga oshdi. Mamlakatimizda so'nggi yillarda kambag'allikni qisqartirish, aholi daro- madlarini oshirish chora-tadbirlari sifatida kichik biznes va xususiy tadbir- korlikni qullab-quvvatlash, rag'batlantirish borasida amalga oshirilayotgan iz- chil tadbirlar, bu buyicha qabul qilinayotgan qator dasturiy yo'nalishlar mazkur softning rivojlanishiga olib kelmokda.

Uzbekiston Respublikasini rivojlantirishning beshta ustuvor yo'nalishi bo'yicha Harakatlar Strategiyasida kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirish ustuvor yo'nalishlardan biri sifatida belgilangan. Jumladan, "Iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirish va liberallashtirishning ustuvor yo'nalishlarida xususiy mulk mulki va kafolatlarini ishonchli ximoya qilishni ta'minlash, xususiy tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes rivoji yo'lidagi barcha to'siq va cheklovlarni bartaraf etish, unga to'liq erkinlik berish, "Agar xalq, boy bo'lsa, davlat xam boy va kuchli bo'ladi" degan tamoyilni amalga oshirish, kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikni keng rivojlantirish uchun qulay ishbilarmonlik muxitini yaratish, tadbirkorlik tuzilmalarining faoliyatiga davlat, xuquqni muxofaza kiluvchi va nazorat idoralari tomonidan noqonuniy aralashuvlarning qat'iy oldini olish vazifalari belgilangan qilishga rag'batlantirishda ularni qullab-quvvatlashga qaratilgan dasturlar, "Yoshlar Daftari" muxim axamiyatga ega bulmoqda. Mazkur yilda "Yoshlar Daftari'ga kiritilgan 430 ming nafar yigit-qizlarning muammolarini hal etish uchun 300 milliard sum mablag' yo'naltirildi. Jumladan, "Temir daftar"dagi oilalar farzandlari bo'lgan 2 mingdan ziyod talabaning kontrakt puli to'lab berildi.

Bu yildan boshlab ish beruvchilarga ularning 25 yoshdan oshmagan ishchi-xodimlari uchun xisoblangan ijtimoiy solik miqdorini byudjetdan to'liq qaytarib berish tartibi joriy qilindi. Natijada joriy yilning ikkinchi yarmida 170 milliard so'm, kelgusi yilda esa 500 milliard so'm mablag' 240 ming nafar yoshni ishga qabul qilgan tadbirkorlar ixtiyorida qoladi. Jaxon mamlakatlarida kambag'allik darajasini kamaytirish uchun turli modellar qo'llaniladi, bu boradagi tajribalarga qisqacha to'xtalib o'tish maqsadga muvofik. Jumladan, shved modeli ishsizlarni uqitish va qayta tayyorlashga aloxida e'tibor qaratib, tulik bandlik va daromadlar tengsizligini kamaytirish dasturlaridan keng foydalanadi. CHexiyada kambag'al axolini moddiy jixatdan qullab-quvvatlash uchun maxsulotlar va pul ko'rinishidagi qo'shimcha ko'maklar nafaqadan tashkari muntazam berib boriladi.

AKSHda kambag'allarga kursatilayotgan yordam axolining 15 foizidan 20 foizigacha qismini qamrab oluvchi moliyaviy vositalar ishlaydi. Ozik-ovqat talonlari, arzon uy-joy olish dasturlari, qariyalar uchun tibbiy va ijtimoiy yordam turlari, bola parvarishlash bo'yicha nafaqalar va boshqa turdagi qullab- quvvatlash turlarini uz ichiga oladi. Yoshlar uchun esa

kasbiy kunikmalari va malakalarini oshirish uchun maxsus dasturlar ajratiladi

Xozirgi iqtisodiyotni modernizatsiyalash sharoitida kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlik nafaqat iqtisodiyotning o'sish sur'atlarini jadallashtirishda, balki mamlakatimiz uchun nihoyatda muxim bo'lgan ish bilan bandlik va mexnat munosabatlarini takomillashtirishda aloxida urin egallaydi. Akademik K.X.Abduraxmonovning fikricha "Kichik biznes - bozor iqtisodiyotining asosi, iqtisodiy o'sish sur'atlarini yalpi milliy maxsulot tarkibi va sifatini, axolining ish bilan bandligi va daromadi darajasini belgilaydigan etakchi sektor xisoblanadi. Shuning uchun butun dunyoda kichik biznesni har taraflama keng rivojlantirishga birinchi darajali e'tibor karatiladi".

Xulosa qilib aytganda, ishlab chiqarishni boshqarish uchun tashkilotdan sifatli maxsulot ishlab chiqarishni tashkil etishning yangi usullarini joriy qilish yoki yangi texnologiyadan foydalanish. Keyingi vaqtlarda mamlakatimizda ro'yxatga olish miqdorining o'sishi, shu jumladan onlayn tartibga 40 daqiqada amalga oshiriladigan ro'yxatga olish jarayonini soddalashtirish hisobiga yuz bermoqda.

Shu o'rinda oldingi ruyxatga olish tizimi bilan joriy ruyxatga olish tizimini solishtirish maksadga muvofiq. Bundan tashqari bozorga an'anaviy maxsulotlarni ishlab chiqarish yoki olib chiqish, shuningdek, ishlab chiqarishni tashkil etish, ishlab chiqarishning texnik elementlari yoki ishlab chiqarishdan tovar sifati tavsifi uzgarishi bilan bog'lik qandaydir yangi elementlari yoki usullarini qo'llash xam samarali tashkil etilmoqda. Davlat va hukumat tomonidan olib borilayotgan. Iqtisodiy, huquqiy, tashkiliy chora-tadbirlar kichik biznesni va tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirishning asosiy yo'nalishini belgilab bermoqda.

Keyingi vaqtlarda barchaning e'tiborida bulgan "YAngi buyuk turg'unlik" nomi bilan atalayotgan koronavirus epidemiyasining keskin tarkalishi iktisodiyotda yangidan yangi iktisodiy isloxotlarni olib borishni taqozo etadi. Mazkur xolatni engib o'tishning samarali chora-tadbirlarini amalga oshirish uchun qiyin ahvolga tushishi mumkin bulgan soxa va tarmoqlarni, yirik korxonalarni iqtisodiy jixatdan qullab-quvvatlash bo'yicha aloxida chora-tadbirlar dasturini ishlab chiqib, amalga oshirish belgilandi. Bu jarayonda: moliya va xomashyo bozorida beqarorlik yuzaga kelishiga yo'l qo'ymaslik, moliyaviy barqarorlikni saqlash hamda bozorlarda narx-navoning o'sishini oldini, iqtisodiyotimizning bazaviy va xal qiluvchi tarmoqlari uzluksiz ishlashini saqlab qolish, markazdan hududiy byudjetlarni va axolimizni qo'llab-quvvatlash asosiy vazifalarimiz bo'lishi belgilandi. Buning uchun har bir tarmoq, korxon va xudud kesimida manzilli va aniq tadbirlarni amalga oshirish lozim bo'ladi. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti SH.Mirziyoev 2021 yil 20 avgust kuni tadbirkorlar bilan ochiq muloqot o'tkazdi. O'zbekistonda tadbirkorlar soni 1,5 million kishini tashkil etadi. Ushbu tadbirkorlarga qarashli, korxonalarda 5 millionga yaqin kishi mexnat qilmoqda. Mamlakatda kredit va subsidiyalar olish, litsenziya, kuchmas mulk va resurslarga ega bo'lish uchun ko'plab shart-sharoitlar yaratilgan, shuningdek, birgina o'tgan 2 yil mobaynida mamlakatimiz xotin-qizlar va yoshlar tadbirkorligini rivojlantirish uchun 500 million AKSH dollari miqdorida sarmoya kiritilgani qayd etildi.

Mamlakatimizda yoshlar o`rtasida kambag`allikni qisqartirish, turmush darajasini oshirish uchun:

- hududlarda mexnatga layoqatli yoshlarning ish bilan bandlik chora-tadbirlarini amalga oshirish, ishsizlik darajasi yuqori bo`lgan joylarda turli dasturlarni amalga oshirishga erishish;
- raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida ish bilan bandlik darajasini oshirish, mexnat bozorini barqarorlashtirishga erishish uchun ishga joylashishga muxtoj shaxslarga kasbiy tayyorgarlik, qayta tayyorlash va malaka oshirish tizimini kengaytirish.
- tirikchilik vositalaridan maxrumlik, tengsizlik, madaniy, ekspluatatsiya kurinishidagi xamda tarkibiy kambag`allikka karshi kurashish borasida kishilarning iqtisodiy tafakkuri va iqtisodiy tarbiyasini o`zgartirishga erishish lozim.

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